

VETERINARY SCIENCES

INFLUENCE OF NATURAL AND CLIMATIC CONDITIONS ON MYCOLOGICAL CONTAMINATION OF CEREAL FEEDS IN SOUTHERN UKRAINE

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ABSTRACT

In the farms of Southern Ukraine during 2014–2024, 753 samples of cereals (corn, wheat, barley, peas) were examined. 75.8% of the samples met sanitary and hygienic requirements, and 24.2% showed changes in organoleptic properties, indicating mycological damage. Of the 559 strains of fungi, 11.5% had high toxicity, 21.6% had low toxicity. The most common fungi were *Aspergillus* (39.1%), *Mucor* (14.1%) and *Fusarium* (13.4%). In wet years, the number of isolates of micromycetes increased by 35–50%, which increased the risk of mycotoxicoses.

Keywords: grain feed, micromycetes, mycotoxins, monitoring, natural and climatic conditions, taxonomic structure of mycobiota.

Introduction

Agriculture in Ukraine is a rather vulnerable sector of the economy to fluctuations in climate change, since the functioning of the crop and livestock sectors, their specialization, and crop yields largely depend on the agro-climatic conditions of the territory and, first of all, on its heat and moisture supply. Changes in the thermal regime of moisture affect the speed of biochemical processes, growth, development and formation of plant productivity, the feed base of livestock farming and its productivity, and, ultimately, on the food security of Ukraine [1].

Since the beginning of the 1980s and up to now, our country has been observing a rather rapid trend towards an increase in the average annual air temperature. Every 10 years, the air temperature in the regions of Ukraine increases by an average of 0.3–0.4 °C, that is, by 1 °C in 30 years [2].

In recent years, the frequency of days with maximum summer temperatures above 35 and 40 °C has almost doubled. In most parts of Ukraine, there is already a trend towards increased drought, an increase in the number and duration of hot periods, and increased fire danger [3, 4].

Climate warming is accompanied by changes in the moisture conditions of a certain territory, the duration and intensity of winter periods are reduced, droughts and other natural phenomena - dry winds, dust storms, downpours, hail, frosts, freezing, icing, floods, inundation, which are associated with climate change - are becoming more frequent [5].

The reduction in the duration and intensity of the winter period, the decrease in the number of frosty days and the depth of soil freezing, lead to the early activation, reproduction and spread of diseases and pests [6].

Changing climatic conditions affect grain feed, the crops of which in Ukraine occupy about 14.5 million hectares, and grain, which contains mainly starch, protein and a small amount of fat, creates an ideal environment for the development of microorganisms, the number of which in one gram can reach from several hundred to several thousand [7].

The development of these microorganisms is one of the possible reasons for the deterioration of the quality of wheat grain and other cereals during storage. Depending on the storage conditions of the grain mass, changes in the numerical and species composition of its microflora may have different characteristics [8].

Since microbial contamination is present at all stages of the grain life cycle – in the field, during harvesting, transportation, storage and processing – the intensity of bacterial contamination can be quite high. Up to 60% of pathogens of bacterial and fungal origin can be transmitted through seeds, which ultimately affects the yield and its quality. The economic losses caused by bacterial and viral infections, mold fungi are difficult to overestimate, since the grain yield of infected plants is reduced by an average of 35–65%, and crop losses can reach 90% [9].

Plants are affected by many pathogenic and spore-forming microorganisms. These are bacteria of the *Enterobacteriaceae* group and mold fungi of the genus *Fusarium* (*F. nivale*, *F. culmorum*, *F. graminearum*, *F. avenaceum*), *Tilletia* (*T. caries* and *T. controversa*), *Cladosporium* (*C. herbarum herbarum*), *Claviceps* (*C. purpurea*), bacteria of the genus *Bacillus*, *Penicillium* spp., *Epicoccum* spp., *Trichothecium* spp., etc. [6–10].

Infection with such microorganisms prevents the normal formation of the crop, and the spores of these bacteria, entering the human and animal body, can cause quite serious disorders of the functioning of the

immune system, gastrointestinal tract, respiratory organs, and nervous system [7, 10].

During the development of microscopic fungi, not only do the physical properties of feed change, but there is also a decomposition of 281 organic substances, with the formation of toxic compounds, which, when consumed by farm animals, can cause poisoning. The temperature factor and humidity of the habitat are one of the decisive factors for the development and growth of both microbes and micromycetes [11–13].

The diversity of the fungal landscape depends on the climatic conditions of natural zones (humidity, temperature, level of insolation, range of soil acidity). The conditions of climatic zones directly affect the formation of soils, their biodiversity, including microscopic fungi. The more southern the region (gray forest soils, chestnut black soils), the more spores are present in relation to the mycelium [14].

The fact of global climate change is beyond doubt, there are changes in all microorganisms, including micromycetes. An assessment of the temperature regime of the 21st century in Ukraine indicates its significant anomaly in relation to the climatic norm [15].

According to Stepanenko S. N. (2007), after 2005, long dry and hot periods were recorded in the southern regions of Eastern Europe and the Mediterranean. The observed global warming of the climate significantly affects the sectors of the economy that depend on climatic conditions, including agriculture. Since the mid-1980s, deviations of individual weather factors from the average long-term values have become significant in the Odessa region, in particular, the number of warm winters has increased, and the average annual air temperature has increased by more than 3.5 °C and the supply of productive moisture in the soil has decreased, which has an extremely negative impact on the state of ecosystems [16].

Most often, agricultural crops are affected by fungi in years of high humidity (rainy summer) during their ripening and harvesting. During such periods, there is a significant spread of *Fusarium* wilt of cereals, which affects large batches of grain. Micromycetes can also develop during storage of feed with high humidity. Long-term storage of grain promotes the development of fungi and the production of new mycotoxins. Thus, new mycotoxins synthesized during grain storage are added to the *Fusarium* toxins formed in the fields [17].

According to available literature, relative humidity of 70–100% promotes the spread of fungi of the genus *Fusarium* spp., and *Fusarium* head blight is most often observed under conditions of high humidity and temperature of 28–30°C, although fungal development is possible at 3–4°C [18]. The optimal temperature for fungal growth is 18–25°C, but the formation of mycotoxins requires lower temperatures - from 4 to 12°C and humidity at 40–50%. Changes in environmental parameters can affect not only the amount, but also the type of mycotoxins formed [19].

Among the great variety of microscopic fungi, representatives of the genera *Aspergillus* and *Fusarium* deserve special attention. It is the fungi of the genus

Fusarium that have been considered the most dangerous toxin-producing in the last 50 years, contaminating both food and feed grains [20, 21].

According to Ukrainian researchers, grain in different regions of Ukraine is often contaminated with representatives of the genera *Fusarium* (26%), *Aspergillus* (21.5%), *Penicillium* (18%), *Alternaria* (12%), etc. [22, 23].

In southern latitudes (on chernozems and red soils) conditions are created for the growth of vegetative mycelium. Due to the high intensity of biological processes in the soil, the available substrate in these zones is quickly exhausted, which leads to the mass formation of spores, the supply of which can be mobilized when portions of biological matter arrive [24].

Systematic mycological studies of feed and feed raw materials for the presence of mold saprophytes will allow not only to determine the taxonomic affiliation and identify toxin-producing species, but will also contribute to the creation of a system of measures to prevent the occurrence of feed toxicosis in farm animals.

The aim of the work was to carry out a comparative analysis of the results of studies on the influence of natural and climatic conditions on the contamination of grain feeds for farm animals with biotic contaminants.

Materials and research methods. The work used the results of monitoring grain feeds (corn, wheat, barley, peas) selected from farms in Southern Ukraine over the past ten years (2014–2024) to assess their contamination with micromycetes under climate change conditions.

The research was conducted on the basis of the laboratory of epizootology, parasitology, monitoring of animal diseases and providing services of the Odessa Research Station of the NSC "IEKVM", the Department of Toxicology, Safety and Quality of Agricultural Products of the NSC "IEKVM".

Samples were taken at the beginning of the harvest and during its storage. The appearance of the grain, color, smell, visible signs of fungal damage were determined. The veterinary and sanitary condition of grain products was established on the basis of generally accepted organoleptic, toxicological and microbiological studies [17, 18].

Organoleptic indicators determined 4 stages of grain damage: the first – malty smell, the color of the cover is not changed; the second – moldy-musty smell, the outer covers are dull, darkened, the endosperm is dark; the third – moldy-rotten smell, the outer covers are dark, the embryo is affected; the fourth – rotten smell, the endosperm is brown.

To establish the total sporulation of grain by micromycetes and determine their species composition, the studied material was spread on Petri dishes with wort agar and incubated at a temperature of 24±0.50 C for 10 days. In parallel, the serial dilution method was used to calculate the content of fungal diaspores in 1 g of feed. Species identification of the isolated isolates of microorganisms was carried out using traditional methods based on cultural and morphological properties by determinants [25–27].

The main test for determining the toxicity of feeds was the skin test on rabbits [28].

Data on precipitation and average air temperature were obtained from the Bolgrad meteorological station (Bolgrad, Odesa region). The HTC indicator according to the Selyaninov method was used to assess the humidification conditions of the period with average daily temperatures higher than 10 °C, i.e. the period of active vegetation. Since in some months of the year there are no active air temperatures above 10 °C, the HTC was not calculated (Selyaninov, 1937).

The hydrothermal coefficient (HTC) was calculated by dividing the amount of precipitation (ΣR) in mm for the period with temperatures above 10 °C by the sum of active temperatures ($\Sigma t_{>10}$) for the same time, reduced by a factor of 10:

$$HTC = \frac{\Sigma R}{0,1 \cdot \Sigma t_{>10}}$$

If $HTC < 0.4$ – very severe drought, from 0.4 to 0.5 – severe drought, from 0.6 to 0.7 – moderate

drought, from 0.8 to 0.9 – weak drought, from 1.0 to 1.5 – sufficiently moist, > 1.5 – excessively moist.

Research results.

The territory of southern Ukraine is located in the southwestern part of the steppe agroclimatic zone. Precipitation is one of the most unstable elements of the climate and, at the same time, its quantity and seasonal distribution in the conditions of southern Ukraine contribute to the wide spread of microscopic fungi and the high frequency of their isolation in plant-based feeds.

According to the hydrothermal coefficient, severe drought was recorded in the South of Ukraine in 2014, 2017, 2022 and 2023. Moderate drought conditions were observed in 2016, 2019 and 2020, while 2015 and 2024 were characterized by weak drought. Only in 2018 and 2021 was a sufficient level of moisture noted (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Parameters of hydrothermal coefficient from 2014 to 2024 in southern Ukraine

In general, southern Ukraine is mostly in moderate or severe drought conditions, and favorable weather in terms of humidity is observed approximately once every two to three years.

According to the results of our research, natural and climatic conditions significantly affect the degree of contamination and species of micromycetes in grain feeds. Temperature factors are often significant for the spread of fungi, can significantly change the species diversity of micromycetes on grain feeds, and the presence of moisture significantly affects the morphogenesis of fungi and their reproduction. The development of mycelium on the surface of both grain and roughage is accompanied by a change in their organoleptic properties and nutritional value.

During 2014–2024, 753 samples of grain feed (corn, wheat, barley, peas) were analyzed in farms in the southern region of Ukraine. It was found that 75.8%

of the samples met sanitary and hygienic requirements. Changes in organoleptic indicators were detected in 24.2% of the samples, indicating their unsatisfactory condition. In particular, contamination with microscopic fungi was recorded; the surface of pea beans had a matte appearance with a gray coating; in samples of grain crops, violations of grain integrity, color change, darkening of the endosperm and germs were observed, especially in corn and wheat, as well as the presence of a malt odor. Similar changes in color, odor, and other physicochemical properties indicate the development of microflora in feeds.

During mycotoxicological studies, 559 isolates of microscopic fungi were isolated, which indicates constant contamination of feed with micromycetes. At the same time, the intensity of the lesion varied depending on the year (Table 1).

Table 1

Results of grain feed research in southern Ukraine in 2014–2024

Year	Number of samples analyzed	Isolates of microscopic fungi identified	% of isolates isolated	Toxicity of isolated micromycetes, %			
				Toxic		Slightly toxic	
				number	%	number	%
2014	50	37	6.6	–	–	18	64.3
2015	66	53	9.6	–	–	8	15.1
2016	94	48	8.7	2	4.2	9	18.8
2017	191	98	17.9	39	39.8	–	–
2018	69	58	10.5	2	3.4	10	17.2
2019	37	17	3.1	–	–	3	17.6
2020	46	65	11.8	5	7.7	17	26.2
2021	67	62	11.3	7	11.3	12	19.4
2022	43	16	3.0	2	12.5	–	–
2023	46	36	6.5	–	–	21	33.3
2024	44	69	12.5	6	8.7	22	31.9
Всього	753	559	100	63	11.5	119	21.6

The largest number of isolates was isolated in 2024 (69 isolates from 44 samples), and the smallest in 2022 (16 isolates from 43 samples). High toxicity was demonstrated by 63 isolates (11.5%), the largest number was in 2017 with 39 isolates (39.8%). Weak toxicity was detected in 119 isolates (21.6%) with peak values in 2023 and 2024 (21 and 22 isolates, respectively).

In grain feeds selected from farms in Southern Ukraine, representatives of the following genera of micromycetes were isolated: *Aspergillus* – 218 isolates,

Mucor – 79, *Fusarium* – 75, *Penicillium* – 64, *Rhodotorula* – 35, *Alternaria* – 30, *Rhizopus* – 25, *Cladosporium* – 18, *Trichothecium* – 13 та *Absidia* – 2 isolates.

Analysis of the taxonomic structure of micromycetes isolated from grain feeds showed the dominance of fungi of the genus *Aspergillus*, the share of which was 39.1% of the total number of isolates (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Structure of the taxonomic composition of micromycetes isolated from grain feeds of farms in Southern Ukraine, %

The second most numerous group was represented by representatives of the genus *Mucor* (14.1%), which indicates their ability to quickly colonize feed, especially under conditions of violation of storage technologies, and fungi of the genus *Fusarium* (13.4%). Moderately represented genera include *Penicillium* (11.4%), *Rhodotorula* (6.3%), *Alternaria* (5.4%) and *Rhizopus* (4.5%). The least represented genera are *Cladosporium* (3.2%), *Trichothecium* (2.3%) and *Absidia* (0.4%), which may indicate their weaker competitiveness.

Natural and climatic conditions have an impact on the degree of contamination and species identity of micromycetes in grain feeds. In years of severe drought, it was found that mycological contamination covers a significant part of grain feed samples. The highest level of fungal contamination was observed in wheat (73%) and corn (66%), somewhat lower in barley (59%) and peas (41%) (Table 2).

Table 2

Taxonomic composition of the mycobiota of grain feeds during years of severe drought in Southern Ukraine

Micromycetes	Grain crop (samples)			
	Corn (n=66)	Wheat (n=73)	Barley (n=59)	Pea (n=41)
	Number of samples with detected microscopic fungi (%)			
<i>Aspergillus</i>	90	88	92	39
<i>Fusarium</i>	49	46	48	–
<i>Penicillium</i>	16	18	–	–
<i>Mucor</i>	22	22	31	31
<i>Rhizopus</i>	12	13	9	16
<i>Alternaria</i>	8	8	7	–
<i>Rhodotorula</i>	3	5	5	–

The dominant genus in all cereals was *Aspergillus* (88 to 92% in cereals, 39% in peas), indicating its high tolerance to drought conditions. *Fusarium* was also frequently isolated from cereal forages (up to 49%), but was not found in peas, which may indicate species specificity or unfavorable conditions for the development of this genus. *Penicillium* was present only in maize and wheat, *Mucor* and *Rhizopus*

in all four crops, although with lower proportions. *Alternaria* and *Rhodotorula* were found only in cereals and absent in peas.

In years with sufficient moisture in southern Ukraine, microbiological analysis of grain feeds (corn, wheat, barley, peas) showed high mycological activity and taxonomic diversity of micromycetes (Table 3).

Table 3

Taxonomic composition of the mycobiota of grain feeds in years with sufficient moisture in southern Ukraine

Micromycetes	Grain crop (samples)			
	Corn (n=29)	Wheat (n=32)	Barley (n=26)	Pea (n=14)
	Number of samples with detected microscopic fungi (%)			
<i>Aspergillus</i>	154	147	144	133
<i>Fusarium</i>	103	94	93	82
<i>Penicillium</i>	30	45	47	50
<i>Mucor</i>	15	12	16	54
<i>Rhizopus</i>	8	3	16	103
<i>Alternaria</i>	9	5	6	–
<i>Rhodotorula</i>	107	105	3	–
<i>Trichothecium</i>	21	–	31	–
<i>Absidia</i>	–	13	–	–
<i>Cladosporidium</i>	–	–	6	–

The dominant genus in all cultures was *Aspergillus*, the number of isolates of which ranged from 133 to 154. Despite the ability of this genus to adapt to low humidity conditions, it also showed high activity in humid environments.

The genus *Fusarium* was found in significant quantities in all crops (82–103 isolates), which is consistent with its high moisture requirements and potential ability to produce mycotoxins. Fungi of the genus *Penicillium* were consistently found in all crops with maximum values in pea samples (50 isolates). The genera *Mucor* and *Rhizopus* were particularly active in conditions of high humidity, the number of which in pea was 54 and 103 isolates, respectively, indicating favorable conditions for their development and possible mold growth of grain products.

Rhodotorula was isolated mainly from corn and wheat, while it was practically not detected in barley and peas, which is associated with the characteristics of the substrate. Fungi of the genera *Trichothecium*, *Absidia* and *Cladosporium* were isolated, which indicates their secondary role in the formation of the feed mycobiota or dependence on specific storage conditions.

Thus, natural and climatic conditions affect the level of contamination of grain feeds with micromycetes and their species composition. In years of severe drought, representatives of 7 genera of micromycetes were isolated, while in years with sufficient moisture – 10. Under conditions of moisture deficiency, *Aspergillus* (detected in 88–92% of samples) and *Fusarium* (in 48–49% of samples) dominated, while the activity of representatives of other genera was significantly lower. The limited species and genus diversity of mycobiota indicates the stressful conditions for its development.

On the other hand, in wet years, an increased mycological load on grain feeds was observed: the number of *Aspergillus* increased by 67.2%, *Fusarium* by 57.2%, *Penicillium* by 34.5%, *Rhizopus* by 20%. This significantly increases the risk of mycotoxicosis in animals. In addition, contamination of cereal samples was recorded with *Trichothecium* fungi in 21% of corn samples and 31% of barley samples, *Absidia* in 13% of wheat samples, and *Cladosporium* in 6% of barley samples.

Conclusions.

Weather conditions in Southern Ukraine have a key impact on the species composition and intensity of contamination of grain feeds by micromycetes. In wet

years, the total number of isolated micromycetes isolates was 35–50% higher than in dry years. In particular, the number of *Fusarium* isolates in wet years increased almost twice as much as in dry years (94–103 versus 46–49). *Rhizopus* was detected 3–5 times more often in wet years, especially in peas (103 isolates versus 16 in the dry period). *Penicillium* was stably present, but in wet years its share increased by 20–30%. In general, in wet years, more genera of micromycetes were recorded, which indicates higher biological activity and risk of mycotoxicosis. In dry years, *Aspergillus* and *Fusarium* prevailed, but with a lower total mycological load.

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